

Study on Thallium (I) Complex of Cyclohexane Dicarboxylic Acid

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Monovariation and Job's continuous variation method by conductometry and spectrophotometry reveal that 1:1 complex is formed between thalious nitrate and cyclohexane dicarboxylic acid (CDA). The stability of the complex determined by Job's method using both conductivity and optical density comes to be about 18×10^{-3} at 28°C.

A large number of complex of dicarboxylic acids with a number of metals have been studied by various workers. We have also made a complete study of composition and stability of thallium(I) complexes¹ formed by some saturated dicarboxylic acids such as oxalic, malonic, succinic, etc. No reference has been found in the literature to cite cyclohexane dicarboxylate complex of any of the metals. Hence we took up the present investigation to compare the complexing nature of CDA with those of other dicarboxylic acids and the stability of thalious cyclohexane dicarboxylate with those of thalious-oxalate,—malonate, —succinate, etc.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental details are the same as described in our previous publications^{2,3}.

A suitable wavelength is selected at which maximum divergence from the additive value would be expected. For this, equimolar metal and ligand solutions are mixed in stoichiometric ratio (as has been previously concluded by conductometric study^{2,3}) and allowed to attain the equilibrium. The optical densities were plotted against the wavelengths. Curve B. of Fig. 1 shows that spectrophotometric measurements for this investigation can be conveniently done between wavelength 250 to 270 m μ . All the measurements were done at 28°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stoichiometry:—In Fig. 1 (curve A) observed conductance is plotted against ml. of Na-CAD added to 5 ml. of thalious nitrate solution (monovariation⁴). A clear break is obtained at the point of addition of 5 ml. of the ligand showing the composition of the com-

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1. K. N. Sahu and A. K. Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, communicated.

2. K. N. Sahu, M. K. Saxena and Arun K. Bhattacharya; *ibid.*, 1962, 39(10).

3. K. N. Sahu and A. K. Bhattacharya, *ibid.*, 1965, 42 (4).

4. I. A. Khan and D. Sen, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1959, 49A, 226.

ml. of ligand added to 5 ml. of $\frac{M}{50}$ thallous nitrate.

Fig. 1.

A - $\frac{M}{50}$ Na-Cyclohexane dicarboxylate (monovalent)
 B - O.D. curve of $\frac{M}{50}$ thallous-cyclohexane dicarboxylate

FIG. 1.

% of Na-Cyclohexane dicarboxylate

Fig. 2

A - $\frac{M}{60}$, B - $\frac{M}{80}$ metal & ligand solution

A' - $\frac{M}{60}$ metal + $\frac{M}{40}$ ligand

B' - $\frac{M}{80}$ metal + $\frac{M}{40}$ ligand

FIG. 2.

% of Na-Cyclohexane dicarboxylate

Fig. 3

A, B - $\frac{M}{20}$ metal and ligand solution (composition)

A', B' - $\frac{M}{20}$ metal + $\frac{M}{20}$ ligand (dissociation)

FIG. 3.

plex to be 1:1. This is further confirmed by Job's⁵ continuous variation method (Fig. 2,

5. F. Job., *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **X**, 9, 113.

curve A and B and Fig. 3, curve A and B). Maxima are obtained exactly at 50% of the metal and 50% of the ligand solution.

Stability:—The dissociation constant (K) of the complex is determined both by conductometry and spectrophotometry. Observations are plotted in Fig. 2 (curve A' and B') and Fig. 3 (curve A' and B'). The value of K is calculated by the formula,

$$K = \frac{C [(p+1)x-1]^2}{(p-1)(1-2x)}$$

where C = molar concentration of the metal solution;

p = molar concentration of ligand/molar conc. of metal; and

x = value of maxima in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 (curves A' and B')

The dissociation constant calculation is summarised in the table below:

TABLE I

Temperature — 28°C.

	Concentration of $TlNO_3$.	Concentration of Na—CDA	Value of x	Calculated value of K
Conductometry study	M/60	M/40	0.47	17.01×10^{-3}
	M/80	M/40	0.455	18.50×10^{-3}
Spectrophotometry study at 255 and 260 m μ	M/50	M/20	0.42	18.41×10^{-3}

The dissociation constant calculated by both methods comes in good agreement with each other.

The stability of thallos cyclohexane dicarboxylate when compared with stabilities of thallos complexes of other dicarboxylic acids¹, it is observed that it lies in between those of oxalate and malonate complexes (K for oxalate= 10.66×10^{-3} and for malonate= 24.28×10^{-3}). It is less than that of oxalate complex probably because of the introduction of a heavy saturated benzene nucleus which causes an increased strain on the carboxylic groups and hence lessens the stability. On the other hand, its greater stability compared to those of malonate, succinate, etc. complexes can be explained as due to the shortening of the distance between the two carboxylic groups.

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